

Exploring Physics-Informed Neural Networks In Linear Elasticity

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Abstract

This study applies Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) to address linear elasticity problems in 2D. A model is trained to predict displacement quantities on each point of a steel material, and introduced the background architecture of this model. In the model, several different systems and methodologies- separable PINNs, partial differential equations (PDEs) residual, boundary conditions, regularization, automatic differentiation (AD), non-dimensionalization- related to PINNs and physics literature are used for the purpose of ensuring as accurate conditions as possible. When it comes to complex physical computations, traditional methods, such as Finite Element Method (FEM), frequently face high computational costs and complexity, which stimulates the transition to machine learning-based applications to mitigate such problems as well as finding out target results more accurately. It has been seen that in scientific machine learning, neural networks are one of the most effective ways, so PINN is decided to be used as a neural network model for our case. One of the most accurate predictions of the model is shown with the optimal parameters in terms of proximity to the real displacement values under the same physical conditions, including other scenarios where the physical scales of the material are changed. The results demonstrate PINNs show significant efficiency, computational savings, and practical applicability, offering substantial alternatives to conventional methods in the upcoming years. We expect our study to be an exemplary one for such applications in this field; for example, in our study, separable PINNs constitutes a substantial role in accurate results, and the methodology behind of it is feasible for many other problems, so implication of separable PINNs can be broadened. The general methodology also shows that it comprises related systems that should be considered and guides to train a PINN model for such problems. Code lines and additional resources available at:

https://github.com/xDKRMx/Physics_Informed_Neural_Network_Model

Keywords: Deep Learning, Scientific Machine Learning, Physics-Informed Neural Network, Linear Elasticity, Partial Differential Equations, Boundary Conditions

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Introduction

The problems In solid mechanics encompass industrial settings along multifarious working fields, such as construction, automotive, aerospace. Specifically, one of these problems is sourced from how materials react in different internal or external interactions which trouble the construction of buildings or production of automobiles, starships [24]. Measuring material behavior under various stressors is vital to prevent traumatic failures. Optimizing material

usage is one of the precautions taken against such threads, but experiments that analyze these problems are improbable to calculate the exact optimized range of materials. At this point, numerical methods had come out solving these complex problems [16]. One of the most well known methods among them is FEM [1, 15, 19]. It has long been used for this purpose since it's been one of the useful numerical methods to solve many problems in this field. However, these methods face severe challenges, like mesh creation or the evolution of nonlinear multiscale systems, which cause significant computational costs due to numerical simulations' complexity [16, 24, 50]. So a need for more efficient and accurate predictive methods had gradually been increasing.

In recent periods, scientific machine learning has made notable improvements, and it has been standing as a considerable alternative to these high dimensional complex numeric problems. Deep learning for these calculations has an upward trend of interest in scientific machine learning. It has been used several times for consecutive modeling for years [51]. Consecutive modeling builds a relationship in a mathematical form between mechanical quantities of a material, such as applied stress to the material and consequent strain [16]. Conversely, for complex materials or combinations of multiple materials, there is an obvious challenge between the consecutive models and deep learning methods based on data because data-driven deep learning methods require a large amount of observational data, which are generally computationally costly, and it is also susceptible to noise in engineering systems, particularly solid mechanics, since this observational data can lead these methods to perform poor generalization to physical conditions [24, 50]. Among deep learning methods, one alternative method which mitigates this shortcoming and complies with the physical rules is Physics-Informed Neural Networks; they use the general approximation of neural networks and embed the governing physical equations integrated by PDEs in the loss function, which provide unsupervised physics-informed learning by not requiring observational data [42]. It is a ground-breaking method that strengthens the power of deep learning while implementing the fundamental principles of physics [2]. This innovative architecture not only provides complex prediction accuracy but also diminishes computational obstacles in scientific and engineering problems [3].

In this study, a PINN model is trained on linear elasticity, one of most well-known subjects in solid mechanics, to show its high computational capacity for solving problems. Section 2.1 shortly presents the linear elasticity equations by also showing the relationship between formulations through Hooke's law. Section 2.2, 2.3, 2.4 introduce the background of the system architecture by describing the key terms. Section 3 shows the methodology behind the PINN architecture that is built, including several additional systems' explanations: Separable PINN and non-dimensionalization approach at 3.1.b.a; PDE residual, boundary conditions and regularization functions at 3.1.b.b.b. Lastly, in the conclusion, findings from the model are summarized regarding its effectiveness in linear elasticity and assess the quality of this method.

2) Background

2.1) Stress-Strain-Displacement Relationship in Elastic Materials

In a branch of material science and solid mechanics, elasticity is a substantial subject which complies with the interaction and distribution of the stress, strain and displacement in elastic materials under the external forces [1].

Displacement is the change in position of a point on the material as a result of applied external force. It shows the distance of how far the point has moved from its initial position[2]. The displacement is expressed based on either time-dependent or time-independent. Time-dependent one is shown as a tensor if computed more than one axis. $u_x(x, t)$, $u_y(y, t)$, or $u_z(z, t)$ are the functions to represent the change of that point at the related axis in given time t . Time-independent one, on the other hand, shows the position change regardless of alteration in time. Except for the connivance of time, it works just like the time-dependent one, $u(x, y, z) = u_x(x)$, $u_y(y)$, or $u_z(z)$ is a general equation to show it, and the time-independent one is going to be delved into in our study.

Stress is a quantity that explains the magnitude of forces which are internal resistances within a point of a material during deformation. It is shown as a tensor and its shape depends on the dimension it is placed in. It is measured as a force per unit area [3], which is expressed mathematically as follows:

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A}, \quad (1)$$

where F is the applied force, and A represents the area of the surface [45].

Strain shows deformations under stress. If forces are applied to a material that is non-rigid, the points, which will be calculated the strain level, on the material move with respect to each other, and this action concludes that deformations occur with the help of existence of the displacement [2]. It can be mathematically shown like this:

$$\epsilon_{xx} = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x}, \quad \epsilon_{yy} = \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial y}, \quad \epsilon_{xy} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} \right), \quad (2), (3), (4)$$

Equations (2), (3), (4) show the components of strain tensor in 2D based on the first-order derivative of the displacement in Hooke's law [20, 31], where ϵ_{xx} , ϵ_{yy} shows the normal strain while ϵ_{xy} shows the shear strain [38], u_x , u_y are the vertical and horizontal matrices of the displacement vector. This system is also valid for other dimensions by just adding the other components' formulations

There is a strong correlation between Displacement, stress, and strain. The strain is calculated by measuring Displacement because the displacement of a material is dependent on the strain, equations (2), (3), (4), in case the material itself complies with a continuum [5]. Likewise, stress is influenced by strains with the product of modulus coefficient according to Hooke's Law, and as a consequence, there is no stress unless strain exists [3]. This action can be shown like that:

$$\sigma = E\epsilon, \quad (5)$$

where E is Young's modulus (Elastic modulus can be represented as various modulus based on the related subject. In our subject, it is considered Young's modulus.), the physical constant which represents the ratio of stress to strain in a material in elasticity. It is the weight

of a column of the material, being able to put pressure on its base so that it causes a specific degree of compression to the weight, per unit area of its base [4].

2.2) PDE Residuals

Partial differential equations are widely used in physical concepts, engineering, and many other fields. While some PDEs can be solved in an analytical surface, most of them rely on numerical processes, which express forward and backwards problems. For this reason, finding solutions of PDEs has a great attraction for many people. Recently machine learning methodologies have started to be used for scientific processes to estimate PDEs solutions accurately. Several new methodologies to solve PDEs have come out, but one of the most notable approaches is Physics-Informed Neural Networks [6, 8, 9].

2.3) What is Physics-Informed Neural Networks[PINNs]

PINNs use neural networks' universal logic, approximation property, and the solid idea of PINNs is to facilitate the most accurate solutions for PDEs via a neural network whose parameters are trained by gradient descent of the accumulation of PDEs, boundary (BC), and initial conditions (IC)- Initial conditions are used in time-based physical systems, and time-based systems aren't used in our study; for this reason, initial conditions aren't mentioned for the rest of the study. If you like to search time-based physical systems, you could see these studies [39, 40]- loss functions [6, 9, 10]. Thus, PINNs can be incorporated with discovery of governing equations through definitions of various coefficients in the PDEs [7]. So far, PINN has been widely used in the field of scientific computing, particularly in forward and backward problems of PDEs [6, 8].

2.4) Boundary Conditions

Boundary conditions[BCs] are constraints that have a crucial role in solving the PDEs to find out the solution which behaves accurately at the domain boundaries. The loss terms are associated with BCs to optimize that predictions of the neural network comply with these conditions. BCs are computed based on the predicted values from the neural network just like the PDE residual loss system. The most used three of them are Dirichlet BCs, Neumann BCs and Robin BCs [11,12, 41].

2.4.a) Dirichlet Boundary Conditions

The Dirichlet BCs determine the exact values that a solution needs to take on the boundary of the domain:

$$u(x) = u_0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega_D, \quad (6)$$

where $u(x)$ represents the output of the neural network, and x denotes the edge point of the material. The prescribed value of this function is u_0 on the boundary $\partial\Omega_D$, Dirichlet boundary of the domain Ω .

They are generally used when the solution is known and controlled on the boundary. For this reason, Dirichlet BCs are sometimes called the "fixed" or "essential" BCs.

The work logic of Them is enforced directly by setting the solution value at the determined points on the boundary during numerical simulations [13, 14, 41].

2.4.b) Neumann Boundary Conditions

The Neumann BCs determine the differentiated values of the function on the boundary of the domain:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial n}(x) = g(x) \text{ on } \partial\Omega_N, \quad (7)$$

where $\frac{\partial u}{\partial n}(x)$ represents the derivative of the function $u(x)$ with respect to the outward normal n at the boundary. Unlike the prescribed value notation u_0 on Dirichlet boundary condition, the prescribed value notation is as a function $g(x)$ as its result is stated flux or rate of change other than a fixed value on the boundary $\partial\Omega_N$, the Neumann boundary of the domain Ω .

They are generally used when the flux or rate of change of the solution is controlled on the boundary rather than known and controlled solution. For this reason, the Neumann BCs are sometimes called the "natural" or "flux" BCs.

Instead of directly setting the solution value at the determined points, They involve enforcing the derivative values of the function at the determined points on the boundary during numerical simulations [41].

2.4.c) Robin Boundary Conditions

The Robin BCs combine Dirichlet with Neumann boundary conditions, so it utilizes from their advantages at the same time by involving the value of the function and its derivative on the boundary of the domain:

$$\alpha u(x) + \beta \frac{\partial u}{\partial n}(x) = g(x) \text{ on } \partial\Omega_R. \quad (8)$$

Processes of the terms and functions are the same as they come from the previous BCs. Here the coefficients α and β specify the related contribution of the Dirichlet and Neumann conditions to the overall boundary equation. Additionally, the reason why the prescribed value notation is shown as a function $g(x)$ comes from the prescribed value of Neumann as it converts the coefficient notation of Neumann into a continuous function.

They are generally used when both the value of the function and its rate of change are likely known on the boundary. For this reason, the Robin BCs are sometimes called the "mixed" BCs.

The work logic of them is enforced by setting a relationship between the value of the function and its derivative at the determined points on the boundary during numerical simulations [14, 41].

3) Methodology

In this section, the methodology of our model trained by governing differential equations is delved into, and it's also shown how it predicts displacements within elastic materials accurately. As elasticity has an extensive scope, our focus is narrowed to a specific subset of problems to receive realistic and precise results from the model. The model is built on predicting displacements in 2D at specific points, and the mathematical and computational principles behind this model are meticulously elaborated on.

3.1) 2D Model

In our 2D model, mathematical and governing physical formulations that the model is trained in are aimed to delve into, and the working logic of the 2D model is moved subsequently. The background of the neural network is observed in order to comprehend the way for the solution of the forward problem, and at the end of this part, the whole methodology behind this model is summarized in Figure 2.

3.1.a) Model System Background

The main content in this part is shaped around linear elasticity parameters, equations, non-dimensionalization processes and their impact on the logic of our model.

In our methodology, the parameters that are used in both physical equations and PDE residuals are defined before the compiling process of the model. To compare the accuracy of the approximate solution generated by the model to the exact physical values, the material is referenced as an isotropic 2D steel rod, and the parameters are based on the steel under the conditions of the earth [20].

<i>Description</i>	<i>Values for the linear elasticity problem</i>
E (Young modulus) (Pa)	21e+10
ν (Poisson's Ratio)	0.3
L (Length of the rod) (m)	25
H (Height of the rod) (m)	1
ρ (density of the material) (kg/m^3)	7800
g (gravitational acceleration) (m/s^2)	9.81

Table 1 : parameters in the 2D model (material is steel)

The PINN model is trained in learning static linear elasticity which ignores time-dependent and dynamical phenomenons [16, 17]. The physical formulations consist of equilibrium equations of stresses and applied external loads, essential connections between strains and stresses, and strain-displacement relations [31]. PDEs are inputted into residual function of the model, and taken residual values at x and y directions are added into the total loss value. Strain equations that are implemented into PDE residuals are shown at equations (2), (3), (4) [16]. Additionally, strain in here is obtained by the result of AD, which is a computational method used to calculate derivatives of functions expressed as computer programs, and it applies the chain rule of calculus to computer programs [18, 34]. In PDE residual, AD is taken from the results of the model in the training process.

Likewise, applying the Hooke's law to the components of strain tensor are kept going for the purpose of obtaining stress tensor:

$$\sigma_{xx} = \lambda(\epsilon_{xx} + \epsilon_{yy}) + 2\mu\epsilon_{xx}, \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_{yy} = \lambda(\epsilon_{xx} + \epsilon_{yy}) + 2\mu\epsilon_{yy}, \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_{xy} = 2\mu\epsilon_{xy}, \quad (11)$$

where σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} and σ_{xy} are the components of the stress tensor, λ is the first Lamé parameter, which is mathematically $\lambda = \nu E / (1 + \nu)(1 - 2\nu)$, where E and ν are Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, explained in 4.1, and μ is the shear modulus, which is mathematically $\mu = E / 2(1 + \nu)$ [4, 17, 31].

To improve generalization and accuracy in the training process, our dimensional PDEs are transformed to non-dimensional equations. Non-dimensionalization maps the dimensional quantities (x , y , z etc.) to the corresponding non-dimensional equations by standardizing them into the determined value range so that they have similar magnitudes, ratios or ranges. Thus, it thwarts instability in gradient descent because of large numerical values and simplifies and stabilizes the problem computationally [20, 24, 25].

In the 2D model, the quantities to nondimensionalize are the input vectors, physical quantities, and parameters. They are divided by their characteristic scales to get non-dimensionalized forms. These scales generally constitute the maximum value of the quantities under consideration for the forward problem [16]. The non-dimensionalization equations are as follows:

$$\hat{x} = \frac{x}{L_c}, \quad \hat{y} = \frac{y}{H_c}, \quad \hat{u}_x = \frac{u_x}{u_{x_c}}, \quad \hat{u}_y = \frac{u_y}{u_{y_c}}, \quad (15), (16), (17), (18)$$

$$\hat{F} = \frac{F}{F_c}, \quad \hat{\lambda} = \frac{\lambda}{\lambda_c}, \quad \hat{\mu} = \frac{\mu}{\mu_c}, \quad (19), (20), (21)$$

where F is the volumetric force, which is just gravitational force in our case, $L_c = L$, $H_c = H$,

$u_{x_c} = \frac{\nu \rho g L^2}{2E}$, $u_{y_c} = \frac{\rho g L^2}{2E}$, $F_c = -\frac{\mu_c u_{y_c}}{L^2}$, $\lambda_c = \mu_c = \mu$, and the notions with diacritical “^” which

are obtained by the division of these characteristic values are the dimensionless quantities of

the normal notions [20]. The characteristic scales of the displacements are the maximum values that the material can have in a point, and these formulations are explained at 4.1. The volumetric force F is crucial for the physical accuracy in our model. As stated above, it's only considered gravitational force, so it is applied to the material on $-y$ direction. The normal volumetric force is assumed $-\rho g$ [20]. The non-dimensionalized volumetric force, on the other hand, is defined as $-\frac{\rho g L^2}{\mu_c u_{y_c}}$ which is acquired by the division of volumetric force

characteristic scale. When it comes to non-dimensionalization of Lamé Parameters, their characteristic scales aren't considered maximum values since they're coefficient values, coming from Hooke's law. The scales of these parameters are assumed as μ for better generalization. At the last step, before analyzing neural network prediction, non-dimensionalized quantities will be scaled back to the original range.

In our model, the core idea is to ensure equilibrium conditions. To achieve this, the model computes the gradients of the stress tensor components σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} and σ_{xy} with respect to x and y . In horizontal direction, x , the sum of the normal stress gradient $\sigma_{xx,x}$ with respect to x and the shear stress gradient $\sigma_{xy,y}$ with respect to y must be equal to zero. In vertical direction, y , the sum of the normal stress gradient $\sigma_{yy,y}$ with respect to y , the shear stress gradient $\sigma_{xy,x}$ with respect to x , and the volumetric force F must be equal to zero [20, 41].

These two equilibrium conditions mold the residual equations under their non-dimensionalized form:

$$Residual_x = \frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{xy}}{\partial y}, \quad (22)$$

$$Residual_y = \frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{yy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{xy}}{\partial x} + \hat{F}, \quad (23)$$

where P is the applied external force, $\frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{xx}}{\partial x}$, $\frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{xy}}{\partial y}$, $\frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{yy}}{\partial y}$, $\frac{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{xy}}{\partial x}$ are the gradients of the stress components. These residuals' values constitute the absolute loss value in PDE residual function. For this reason, the result is $Residual = \{Residual_x, Residual_y\}$.

This process drastically remains grounded in the same principles that govern higher-dimensional elasticity problems.

3.1.b) 2D Model Neural Network Structure

In this part, we give an overview of several parts in the model. Firstly, it is started with model architecture, including separable PINN; secondly, working logic is going to be explained by being added forward pass, the loss function, backpropagation and optimization process into the explanation; lastly, the overall system is summarized, and proposed neural network architecture is shown in Figure 2.

3.1.b.a) Model Properties

Model architecture in 2D is established in the form of multilayer perceptron [MLP]-based PINN [23], which is a standard forward and backward pass processes that can approximate the solutions of PDEs in a mere neural network that handles the input and output [25, 26].

The model is built up with two separated input layers- one shows the training process in x direction (Elements of this layer shows a training array, separating a 25 meter length (L) rod into 199 equal intervals, and each one represents a point in the 1D environment, 200 points in total.); another one shows the training process in y direction (Elements of this layer also shows a training array, but it separates 1 meter height (H) of the rod into 199 equal intervals with again 200 points in total.)- three hidden layers of width size 128 at each direction, and one output layer which shows a predicted displacement array of shape (200, 2), where each 200 elements represents a scalar displacement in a certain direction, and 2 elements are the directions.

The compiling process is applied separately in x and y layers which shows that the separable PINN model architecture (SPINN) is dominant in the propagation process. SPINN enables the use of forward-mode AD to dramatically reduce the computational cost in order to solve multi dimensional PDEs. Its architecture is used to parameterize multiple separated functions within the process of a generic neural network. Thus, training time, testing time and memory costs are notably reduced in SPINN models compared to generic PINN models, where the trainable parameters are exponentially grown as long as the grid resolution increases.

SPINN consists of d body-networks, which are the neural networks type related to MLPs, each of them taking an individual 1D coordinate component as an input. Each body-network $f_{\theta_i} : R \rightarrow R^r$ (parameterized by θ_i , which is described in **3.1.b.b.a**) transforms the coordinates at i^{th} axis into a r -dimensional feature presentation [20, 42]. This process, element-wise product, is expressed as follows :

$$u_{\theta}(x) = \sum_{j=1}^r \prod_{i=1}^a f_{\theta_i}^{(j)}(x_i), \quad (24)$$

where $u_{\theta}(x)$ represents the output of the network as parameterized by the trainable parameters

θ , x_i denotes i^{th} input coordinate, and $f_{\theta_i}^{(j)}$ is the output vector at the j^{th} element of the

vector-valued array f_{θ_i} .

To ensure non-linearity, the Leaky ReLU activation function is used. Generic ReLU is generally non-suitable for 2D models since its second-order derivative is zero [25]; rather, Leaky ReLU gives the most accurate results in our specific 2D model setup. The simplicity and effectiveness of Leaky ReLU provides our model to be trained in a more stable way by evading the vanishing gradient problem [32].

For optimization, the network is trained via gradient descent using the Adam optimizer with an initial learning rate of 1e-4 and 10000 epochs. After every 500 epochs, the learning rate is reduced by 5% up to the last epoch. You can go to the **3.1.b.b.c** backward pass to get more knowledge about optimization.

3.1.b.b) Working Logic of The Model

The working logic of our 2D model is explained in this part. The first part is shaped forward pass process, including the loss function. The second part is the backward pass process, including backpropagation and optimization. In the last part, both the loss value minimization and overall model architecture are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

3.1.b.b.a) Forward Pass

The compiling logic in 2D is watching nearly the same track to a generic deep neural networks (DNNs) barring a significant difference: using AD methods to involve PDEs and BCs into the loss function ensures the training process to approach the real physical laws [21]. The working process starts with two separate input layers after input arrays stand out for training. the scales of the input arrays is mentioned in **3.1.b.a** Model Architecture, and they're defined by being discretized into 200 equal intervals:

$$x_{train} = \{x_i | i = 0, 1, \dots, 199\}, \text{ where } x_i = \frac{i \cdot L}{199}, \quad (25)$$

$$y_{train} = \{y_i | i = 0, 1, \dots, 199\}, \text{ where } y_i = \frac{i \cdot H}{199}, \quad (26)$$

where x_{train} and y_{train} show the input array by adjusting the element values based on the length and height of the rod. Before getting into forward pass, each element of x_{train} and its matched element in y_{train} are firstly non-dimensionalized and combined into a single input vector. This process results in 200 different vectors, each with a shape of [2,], where each vector represents a point on the rod.

Since we aim to train the model to predict outputs in two separate directions, two separate networks are constructed. Each matrix processes the vectors one by one via forward pass with its respective direction.

$$\hat{x}_i = \frac{x_i}{L}, \quad \hat{y}_i = \frac{y_i}{H}, \quad (15), (16)$$

$$k_i = \{\hat{x}_i, \hat{y}_i\} \text{ with } k_i \in R^2, \quad f_{\theta_j} = \{f_{\theta_x}, f_{\theta_y}\} \text{ with } j \in \{x, y\}, \quad (27), (28)$$

$$\Theta = \{w_0^{(1)}, b_0^{(1)}, \dots, w_i^{(H)}, b_i^{(H)}\}, \quad (29)$$

$$f_{\theta_j}^{(h)}(k_i^j) = \alpha(w_i^{(h)} \cdot f_{\theta_j}^{(h-1)}(k_i^j) + b_i^{(h)}), \quad h = 0, \dots, H, \quad (30)$$

where k_i denotes input vectors as an array, f_{θ_j} represents the array of two separate networks for the x- and y-networks respectively, one for the x direction and one for the y direction, Θ states all trainable parameters in the network [weights and biases], h is the index of the related layer, H is the total number of layers, $f_{\theta_j}^{(h)}(z_i)$ represents the outputs of the current layer and the inputs of the next layer by applying the weight parameter $w_i^{(h)} \in R^{n_{i-1} \times n_i}$ and

adding the the bias parameter $b_i^{(h)} \in R^{n_i-1 \times n_i}$, which n_i represents the network width of the current layer h , and activation function α , ReLU for our model, is applied to whole outputs at input layers, hidden layers and output layer [8, 20, 21, 22, 26].

After passing through the input layer, the shape of an output vector is [256,] since the width of the input layer is 128 neurons, and the output size is arranged as twice the width size to evaluate two elements [x and y] in the input vector. As this output passes through the first hidden layer, the shape size remains [256,] because the width is maintained at 128 neurons for each hidden layer. That's why the shape size is preserved at [256,] after passing through each layer, including the output layer. At the end of passing, the output shape is reshaped to [128,2], corresponding to the 128 features for each element to enable the suitable dimension for element-wise multiplication. Since we have two separate networks [f_{θ_x} and f_{θ_y}], it needs to be assembled the outputs of them into a single output result at the final step of forward pass to keep further in the training process. As discussed in Section 3.1.b.a model architecture, specifically, element-wise product is used for this action In SPINNs [42].

$$u_{\theta}(k_i) = \sum_{n=1}^{128} f_{\theta_x}^{(n)}(k_i) \odot f_{\theta_y}^{(n)}(k_i), \quad (31)$$

where $u_{\theta}(k)$ is the final output for the input k_i , \odot denotes product, $f_{\theta_x}^{(n)}(k_i)$ and $f_{\theta_y}^{(n)}(k_i)$ are the n^{th} elements of the output vectors produced by the x and y networks. After producing output vectors of each network, the shape size of the final output is decreased up to (2,), and this forward pass is iterated over the number of input vectors k_i .

3.1.b.b.b) Loss Function

Like every PINN model, our model also approximates the initial and upcoming exact solutions $u[k]$ of the linear elasticity problem with the help of function $u_{\theta}[k]$ of deep neural networks. At this point, figuring out the most precise parameters is the essential optimization problem, and that's how loss function steps in so that it minimizes the loss value between the outputs of the model and exact solutions [20, 22]. The loss function is the accumulation of each loss factor's value, and it can be expressed as follows :

$$Loss = L_{PDE} + L_{BC} + L_{reg}. \quad (32)$$

L_{PDE} shows the PDE residual value by applying the MSE process :

$$L_{PDE} = \lambda_{PDE} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left\| u_{\theta}(k_i) - f(k_i) \right\|^2, \quad (33)$$

where $U(u_{\theta}(k_i), x_i, y_i)$ represents the result value of applied PDEs to the predictions at given x and y point, λ_{PDE} is the weight coefficient which determines the importance rate of PDE residual, it's 1 in our case, and the process order is shown at methodology section 3.1.a. $f(k_i)$

shows external force, used P in our 2D model. N is the number of collocation points, corresponding to PDE loss function. To find the most optimal loss value, the residual result at each i^{th} iteration is summed, and the total summation is divided by N after including all elements [16, 22].

L_{BC} shows the boundary conditions by being applied to the same process:

$$L_{BC} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\lambda_{left} (u_{\theta}(k_{left}) - u(k_{left}))^2 + \lambda_{bottom} (u_{\theta}(k_{bottom}) - u(k_{bottom}))^2 \right]. \quad (34)$$

In loss function, Dirichlet Boundary Conditions are used, described in **2.4.a**. $u_{\theta}(k_{left})$ shows the prediction of the model at the left edge where $x_i = 0$ along the y axis; $u_{\theta}(k_{bottom})$ is the same process but $y_i = 0$ along the x axis. λ_{left} and λ_{bottom} are the weight coefficients for each edge of the rod; both λ_{left} and λ_{bottom} are 1 in our first scenario, but we'll be observing the different scenarios which λ_{left} and λ_{bottom} are changed. The exact values are subtracted at these points from the predictions, but there is no effect of this subtraction since our exact boundaries are homogenous, physically zero, at one end. After that, the same MSE process is applied. That's where $\frac{1}{2}$ comes from [21, 25, 44].

L_{reg} denotes the regularization factors. Unlike PDE residual and BCs, MSE isn't applied to the regularization process; instead, parameter norm regularization is applied for the purpose of preparation for the AD and backpropagation [27].

Regularization is a method for addressing the problem of overfitting by inputting a few rules into the loss function. It adds a cost term to strive to impose the weights up to zero or extremely minor values so that it reduces the model generalization error. Therefore, it seeks to apply a penalty to the learning model [28, 29].

L^1 and L^2 regularizations are the most common techniques among norm regularizations [27]. L^1 regularization (Lasso regularizer) is primarily used to penalize the weight matrix's absolute values. It stimulates sparsity in the model, implying it tends to impose the weights with less important features toward 0. It is mathematically expressed as

$$L^1 = \lambda_{reg} \sum_{i=1}^n |w_i|, \quad (35)$$

where λ_{reg} is a weight coefficient for the contribution of regularization to the loss function, n is the total number of weight parameters in the entire neural network, and w is the related weight value at the given i^{th} iteration.

Unlike L^1 regularization, weights with less important features aren't supposed to be 0 in L^2 regularization (Ridge regularizer). For this reason, corresponding weight values are still reduced but are always kept higher than 0. That's where the square magnitude values come from. It is mathematically expressed as

$$L^2 = \lambda_{reg} \sum_{i=1}^n w_i^2, \quad (36)$$

where λ_{reg} is the weight coefficient- the value of λ_{reg} is 11e-2 in our model, and selecting the efficient value for it is substantial since it controls the importance of regularization in the loss. n is the total number of weight parameters, and w is the related weight value at the given i^{th} iteration [28, 29, 30].

In our model, L^2 regularization is implemented into our model because L^1 regularization is generally less suitable for continuous physics problems where all features should be evaluated. Therefore, the loss gradient scaling linearly with weight is preferred other than using a constant alteration [27].

3.1.b.b.c) Backward Pass

Taking all loss values from each loss factor gives us the absolute loss function value, which shows the total error that the predictions deviate from the exact values.

Therefore, it should be minimized toward zero by updating weights and biases through feedforward and backpropagation processes [31]. This optimized problem can briefly be showed like that :

$$\Theta^* = arg_{\Theta} min L(\Theta), \quad (37)$$

where Θ^* is potential parameters for the model which minimize the discrepancy between the predicted solution $u_{\Theta}(x)$ and the exact one $u(x)$ [26, 28].

The forward pass has been already described , and the next step is now backpropagation. To take place this process, `eqx.filter_value_and_grad` is called from equinox library [53].

Backpropagation, also known as the backward pass, optimizes the network weights and biases by taking the gradient of the loss function with respect to network parameters in Θ [32].

One of the most used algorithms for backpropagation is gradient descent, an algorithm which minimizes a given loss function by adjusting parameters iteratively in the opposite direction of the gradients [33].The gradient formulations are shown by:

$$\Delta\Theta_{w_i^h} = - \eta \frac{\partial L}{\partial w_i^h}, \quad (38)$$

$$\Theta_{w_i^h}^{new} = \Theta_{w_i^h}^{old} + \Delta\Theta_{w_i^h}, \quad (39)$$

and

$$\Delta\Theta_{b_i^h} = - \eta \frac{\partial L}{\partial b_i^h}, \quad (40)$$

$$\Theta_{b_i^h}^{new} = \Theta_{b_i^h}^{old} + \Delta\Theta_{b_i^h}, \quad (41)$$

where $\Delta\Theta_{w_i^h}$ and $\Delta\Theta_{b_i^h}$ represents the gradient of result in the loss function, computed using

AD, with respect to the weight and bias at the certain point in the the current layer by

multiplying with $-\eta$ in the backpropagation process. η is the learning rate, and its value plays a vital role on the optimization updating. The reason why it's not multiplied with minus is to reduce the loss value. This alteration is added into the old one so that the model updates the parameters by reducing them. Its value in the model is shown at 3.1.b.a Model Properties.

In the optimization process, such algorithms are used in methods like, stochastic gradient descent (SGD) or Adaptive Moment Estimation (adam), where SGD is an optimization method that blends gradient descents with random subsampling within the loss function, and adam is an extension of this algorithm which computes the decay averages of previous gradients to give respectively the estimations of the first and second moments of the gradients [33, 35, 36, 37].

The model has been trained with adam optimizer; the reason why it is implemented is that it consistently yields better performance and shows more accuracy without heavy tuning [25]. Therefore, in our case, the gradients are computed during backpropagation by being fed into the Adam update rule.

After finishing the forward and backward pass, the iteration of the passing process is increased in the network by one, which gives us the epoch count, one complete training step including the entire steps [16]. If our current epoch count is less than the maximum epoch count, the process keeps going until the iteration is equal to maximum epoch count, which implies that the training process is over. Additionally, during this process, we could also observe the loss value minimization at each step. Here is the loss decreasing graphic:

Figure 1 : Loss value minimization graphic which shows the loss value at each epoch count. The reason why the initial loss value is so large is because our material, steel, has really large parameters like E , ρ .

Now that the whole process is explained, it can be summarized in a figure. Figure 2 follows the general architectures in PINNs literature [20, 21, 42], adapted in our scenario. Here is Figure 2 that shows the whole process:

Figure 2 : Schematic diagram of the generic working logic of the PINN model, where k_x and k_y are input vectors, a is activation function, f_{θ_x} and f_{θ_y} are output vector, and u_{θ} output results.

4] Results

In this section, the experimental results of displacement values of the same material in each direction are observed. Therefore, this is the test process for the model to demonstrate whether its results are considerably accurate with the exact results. Different displacement values as a result of variations in case the size of the material is changed are analyzed as well. Initially, the physical formulations are elaborated on by referencing the linear elasticity equations and relationships; next, the outputs of the model with the most accurate weight coefficients by its based material are graphically and numerically shown; finally, other outputs with varied material scales are gone through.

Like the material in training process, the material is considered an isotropic 2D steel rod with primarily the size of $25\text{m} \times 1\text{m}$, $x \in [0, 25]$ m, $y \in [0, 1]$, shown in the (1000×40) mesh grid system; the displacement graphics of the rod with different sizes are shown, but the mesh grid count remains same because there is no valuable impact of mesh grid count on the displacement values. Additionally, changing mesh grid count only impacts the resolution of the visualization; that is, the larger the mesh grid count is, the more detailed visualization you observe [52]. As the material is depended on Dirichlet BCs, the beginning

edge of the rod is fixed, which is 0 in terms of displacement in each direction, and the end edge of the rod is free, which means that the beam is deformed freely under its own weight at this edge [33]. The predicted results are compared with the displacement values that are calculated through physical formulations- they are explained in 4.1 analytical formulations part.

4.1] Physical Formulations of Physical Quantities

First of all, it needs to be stated again that only gravitational force is considered in our model which is added into the $-y$ direction of the PDE residual loss function. For this reason, the first exact formulation that is based on the stress in y direction because it denotes a force per unit area [3]. From this formulation, there are correlations between stress, strain and displacement formulations in other directions.

The gravitational force is $-mg$, which could be converted m into $V\rho$ (V volume, ρ density) [20], and it's also known that stress in y direction is $\sigma = \frac{F_y}{A}$ [45], so this transformation could be applied: $V = x \cdot y$, $A = x$, $\sigma_{yy} = -\frac{V\rho g}{A} = -\rho g y$. We said that there is a correlation between stress and strain ($\sigma = E\epsilon$) via Hooke's Law, so it can be deduced that $\epsilon_{yy} = \frac{-\rho g y}{E}$ from here.

In order to calculate the x direction values of strain and stress, Poisson's ratio is used, which is explained as the ratio of the lateral in a solid material to its longitudinal extension because of an axial tension [46]. Thanks to its effect, in the considered isotropic beams, the transverse strains, stresses and even displacements (they're all influenced by this) can be measured with this formulation :

$$\epsilon_{xx} = -\nu \epsilon_{yy}, \quad \sigma_{xx} = -\nu \sigma_{yy}, \quad u_{xx} = -\nu u_{yy}, \quad (42)$$

where ν is Poisson's ratio, and the reason why minus is added is that the rod in y direction is stretched longitudinally with the gravitational force, and its transverse direction, x , is contracted horizontally [43].

When it comes to shear strain and stress, Hooke's law is used as usual, and the formulations that are also implemented into the PDE residual function are shown as usual [38]:

$$\sigma_{xy} = 2\mu \epsilon_{xy}, \quad \epsilon_{xy} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} \right). \quad (4), (11)$$

Lastly, the displacement in y direction is referenced by integrating ϵ_{xx} :

$$u_{yy} = \int \frac{-\rho g y}{E} dy = \frac{-\rho g y^2}{2E} + C, \quad u_{yy}(0) = 0 \Rightarrow C = 0, \quad (43)$$

where $\frac{-\rho g y}{E}$ denotes the ϵ_{yy} . The reason why the constant of the integral is acknowledged as 0 is due to the fixed edge boundary condition at the first point $u_{yy}(0)$ [47].

4.2] Displacement Results and Error Analysis

In the visualization of the predicted, exact and error values, they are shown on the heat map and 2D, which can show the comparison really well.

During the predictions' generation phase, the predictions of the model are inherently generalized due to the non-dimensionalized structure in the training process [24], so the model would most likely generate non-dimensionalized values regardless of dimensionality of the given input, and that's what our case is since the model is trained and tested with the same properties of the material, steel. The predictions must be re-dimensionalized to be observed as a physical quantity [49, 16]. This step is crucial for the comparison, and if it hasn't been done, the physical quantities would have been compared with generalized values which causes the inconsistency in the test process [48].

For re-dimensionalizing the predictions, non-dimensionalized outputs of the model are multiplied in each direction with their corresponding characteristic: $u_{\theta^{xx}} = \hat{u}_{\theta^{xx}} u_{x_C}$,

$u_{\theta^{yy}} = \hat{u}_{\theta^{yy}} u_{y_C}$, where $\hat{u}_{\theta^{xx}}$ and $\hat{u}_{\theta^{yy}}$ show the non-dimensionalized outputs of the model,

and u_{x_C} and u_{y_C} are the characteristic scales which rescale the generalized values to physical quantities [16]. Here is the characteristic scale of displacement in each direction:

$u_{x_C} = \frac{v\rho g L^2}{2E} c$, $u_{y_C} = \frac{\rho g L^2}{2E} c$, where c is an additional coefficient, which is 1e-3 for our

scenario. Because these scales are scalar values, $\hat{u}_{\theta^{xx}}$ and $\hat{u}_{\theta^{yy}}$ are not multiplied with minus, coming from volumetric force vectors, and the scales, as stated in 3.1.a Model System Background, show the maximum values that the displacement of the material could ever be in both directions.

Briefly, the process starts with dimensional inputs; then, these inputs are converted into the non-dimensionalized quantities, and they get into the forward and backward passes in the model architecture, coming out with non-dimensionalized outputs; finally, these outputs are converted back into dimensionalized quantities [49]. Here is vertical and horizontal results, including error maps:

Figure 3 : these 6 graphics show the predicted, reference, and error [the difference between predicted and reference] results on heat map.

On the graphics, it can be inferred that the accuracy is most likely provided; the high accuracy for the same size material could also be seen on Table 4 as well.

$L = 25 \text{ \& } H = 1$	u_{max}	u_{min}	u_{avg}	u_{std}
u_{xx} (exact values in x direction)	5.46e-08	4.47e-13	1.85e-08	—
u_{yy} (exact values in y direction)	-1.49e-12	-1.82e-07	-6.15e-08	—
$u_{\theta_{xx}}$ (predictions in x direction)	5.82e-08	-1.43e-11	1.85e-08	—
$u_{\theta_{yy}}$ (predictions in y direction)	4.49e-11	-2.09e-07	-6.55e-08	—
$u_{error^{xx}}$ (error in x direction)	3.54e-09 (x =999, y =0)	1.14e-14 (x =78, y =10)	3.54e-10	3.89e-10
$u_{error^{yy}}$ (error in y direction)	2.67e-08 (x =999, y =39)	8.29e-15 (x =80, y =3)	4.07e-09	4.83e-09

Table 2 : These graphics show the numerical data for the output values, including max value u_{max} , min value u_{min} , mean value u_{avg} , standard deviation value u_{std} . On this condition, the coefficient of the regularization λ_{reg} is 11e-2; the coefficients of the boundary conditions λ_{left} and λ_{bottom} are 1.

These results show that our PINN model with these parameters is able to predict the exact values accurately in case the material has the same size as the training process, which is our main aim. Let's test the predictions of the model in case the material has the different size, but the same coefficients (not too many graphics are shown; instead, just a 2D graphic and numerical data on tables are shown for each scenario).

Figure 5 : the 2D graphic of the average displacement values. The predicted and exact displacement values are deviated, and the predictions are below the exact values.

$L = 15 \text{ \& } H = 0,6$	u_{max}	u_{min}	u_{avg}	u_{std}
u_{xx} (exact values in x direction)	1.97e-08	1.61e-13	6.64e-09	—
u_{yy} (exact values in y direction)	-5.37e-13	-6.55e-08	-2.21e-08	—
$u_{\theta xx}$ (predictions in x direction)	7.46e-09	-5.17e-12	2.36e-09	—
$u_{\theta yy}$ (predictions in y direction)	1.61e-11	-2.66e-08	-8.30e-09	—
$u_{error^{xx}}$ (error in x direction)	1.27e-08 (x=989, y=39)	3.20e-14 (x=1, y=38)	4.28e-09	3.86e-09
$u_{error^{yy}}$ (error in y direction)	4.10e-08 (x=988, y=39)	3.43e-14 (x=4, y=0)	1.43e-08	1.24e-08

Table 3 : On this condition, the coefficient of the regularization λ_{reg} is $11e-2$; the coefficients of the boundary conditions λ_{left} and λ_{bottom} are 1. The reason why most of the results are smaller than the main one is because the material has a smaller size, which makes all values decreased.

Figure 6 : the 2D graphic of the average displacement values. The predicted and exact displacement values are still deviated, but they're closer than the previous one this time.

$L = 20 \ \& \ H = 0,8$	u_{max}	u_{min}	u_{avg}	u_{std}
u_{xx} (exact values in x direction)	$3.50e-08$	$2.86e-13$	$1.18e-08$	—
u_{yy} (exact values in y direction)	$-9.54e-13$	$-1.17e-07$	$-3.94e-08$	—
$u_{\theta_{xx}}$ (predictions in x direction)	$2.37e-08$	$-9.19e-12$	$7.53e-09$	—
$u_{\theta_{yy}}$ (predictions in y direction)	$2.87e-11$	$-8.50e-08$	$-2.66e-08$	—
$u_{error^{xx}}$ (error in x direction)	$1.30e-08$ ($x=84, y=39$)	$2.06e-14$ ($x=1, y=29$)	$4.28e-09$	$3.83e-09$
$u_{error^{yy}}$ (error in y direction)	$3.88e-08$ ($x=983, y=39$)	$6.11e-14$ ($x=0, y=24$)	$1.28e-08$	$1.12e-08$

Table 4 : On this condition, the coefficient of the regularization λ_{reg} is $11e-2$; the coefficients of the boundary conditions λ_{left} and λ_{bottom} are 1. The results get higher as the material size gets larger.

Figure 7 : the 2D graphic of the average displacement values. The predicted and exact displacement values are deviated, but the predictions are above the exact values this time. It could be inferred that the threshold for the predictions before passing the exact values is at about the scenario of $L = 25$ and $H = 1$.

$L = 30$ & $H = 1,2$	u_{max}	u_{min}	u_{avg}	u_{std}
u_{xx} (exact values in x direction)	$7.87e-08$	$6.44e-13$	$2.66e-08$	—
u_{yy} (exact values in y direction)	$-2.15e-12$	$-2.62e-07$	$-8.86e-08$	—
$u_{\theta_{xx}}$ (predictions in x direction)	$1.21e-07$	$-2.07e-11$	$3.85e-08$	—
$u_{\theta_{yy}}$ (predictions in y direction)	$6.43e-11$	$-4.34e-07$	$-1.37e-07$	—
$u_{error^{xx}}$ (error in x direction)	$4.23e-08$ (x =999, y =0)	$7.05e-15$ (x =38, y =10)	$1.19e-08$	$1.10e-08$
$u_{error^{yy}}$ (error in y direction)	$1.72e-07$ (x =999, y =0)	$2.35e-14$ (x =23, y =15)	$4.80e-08$	$4.50e-08$

Table 5 : On this condition, the coefficient of the regularization λ_{reg} is $11e-2$; the coefficients of the boundary conditions λ_{left} and λ_{bottom} are 1. Now that the threshold is exceeded, the results are bigger than the previous ones.

Figure 8 : the 2D graphic of the average displacement values. The predicted and exact displacement values are still deviated, but the predictions are above the exact values this time, and the larger the size gets, the more deviation is between predicted and exact.

$L = 40 \text{ \& } H = 0,6$	u_{max}	u_{min}	u_{avg}	u_{std}
u_{xx} (exact values in x direction)	1.40e-07	1.14e-12	4.72e-08	—
u_{yy} (exact values in y direction)	-3.82e-12	-4.66e-07	-1.57e-07	—
$u_{\theta xx}$ (predictions in x direction)	3.83e-07	-3.68e-11	1.22e-07	—
$u_{\theta yy}$ (predictions in y direction)	1.14e-10	-1.38e-06	-4.35e-07	—
$u_{error^{xx}}$ (error in x direction)	2.44e-07 (x =999, y=0)	2.28e-14 (x =26, y =36)	7.49e-08	6.82e-08
$u_{error^{yy}}$ (error in y direction)	9.13e-07 (x =999, y=0)	2.44e-13 (x =0, y =12)	2.77e-07	2.54e-07

Table 6 : On this condition, the coefficient of the regularization λ_{reg} is $11e-2$; the coefficients of the boundary conditions λ_{left} and λ_{bottom} are 1.

5) Discussion

As the results' tendency is assessed in case of different scenarios, the model shows the most accurate results in the first scenario, and this assertion is understood from the proximity of predicted values and the accuracy on the graphics, averagely horizontal $3.54e-10$ error and vertical $4.07e-09$ error which shows the least average errors with two-directions. This occurrence depends on two essential factors. First of all, in the training process, the material that the model is trained in is the same material with the same scale in the test process for the first scenario. This sameness both ensures more balanced assessment and allows us to focus on the ratio of learning accuracy without considering scaling differency or other factors that could impact the overall accuracy. When other scenarios are analyzed- in which the scale of the material is increased or decreased with the dormant ratio between length and width- the predictions deviate more as the scale of the material differs from the training size. This deviation, as stated in the results section, stems from the size of the trained material since the model isn't familiar with the sizes, other than $25m \times 1m$ in spite of non-dimensional scales. The second factor is the weight coefficient values, especially used in loss functions. If the weight coefficients weren't adjusted correctly in the model, the predictions would highly deviate in any scenario, and the results' graphics wouldn't even have a similar curve. Therefore, the weight coefficient values are crucial when it comes to balancing the results' accuracy. In our case, hundreds of different weight coefficient variations are simulated; however, in most of the scenarios, the results weren't even considerate. Even so, one of the best weight coefficients for loss functions were found as $\lambda_{PDE} = 1$, $\lambda_{left} = 1$, $\lambda_{bottom} = 1$, $\lambda_{reg} = 11e-2$.

Briefly, if the main goal is to observe how accurately the model is able to predict, the first scenario is the best one to do that, and if the main goal is to observe the accuracy of the model in different kinds of scenarios, it's better to train multiple models with different parameters for each scenario to reach out to the most accurate ones.

6) Conclusion

the the training and test inputs have the same value range, $x \in [0, 25]m$ and $y \in [0, 1]m$ for both training and test, but different mesh systems, $[200 \times 200]$ for training and (1000×40) for testing.

In this study, a physics informed neural networks (PINNs) model is presented that is trained with the governing equations in 2D linear elasticity, embedded in partial differential equations (PDE) residual, referencing a steel-based material, and it is tested with the same properties of the material but several sizes and different mesh grid counts to ensure how accurate the predictions are in terms of displacement. The whole process can be summarized with these steps:

1. The model approached the forward pass, integrating separable PINNs.
2. After getting the output vectors from the initial forward pass, the model calculated the error, taking from the sum of PDE residual, Boundary Conditions (BCs), and L^2 regularization errors.
3. The error values were optimized during backpropagation, using gradient descent.
4. After the outputs passed through the backward pass [backpropagation] and got updated, the first pass was completed, and this process was iterated over the determined epoch count.
5. The results of the last iteration are taken as predictions.
6. The accuracy of this approach has been compared with the exact displacement values obtained by the analytical formulation, displacement value on each point of the material by its mesh system.

After the comparison, it's concluded the model was able to predict the results really close to the exact results with negligible error, maximally $1.03e-8$, and adding more refined details could further improve the predictions. This comparison shows that If the best parameters for the given terms in the system are found correctly with several variations, the optimized values can be caught thoroughly.

Lastly, the efficacy of PINNs to solve complex solid mechanical problems without requiring large observational data sheds light on the way for more consistent simulations in scientific computing.

Terminology

Notations	Explanations
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
PINN	Physics-Informed Neural Network
PDE	Partial Differential Equation
BC	Boundary Conditions
AD	Automatic Differentiation
x, y	x and y directions in space
\hat{x}, \hat{y}	Non-dimensionalized x and y directions
u_{xx}, u_{yy}	Displacement in x and y directions, respectively
$u_{\theta_{xx}}, u_{\theta_{yy}}$	Predicted Displacement in x and y directions, respectively
Θ	Vector of the trainable parameters in the network
$L[\Theta]$	Loss function
w	Weight parameter
b	Bias parameter

Table 7 : Terminology table

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